

Design of an Impact/Force Switching Controller

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Abstract—Intelligent interaction control is required in many fields of application. Being able to switch between optimized controllers based on specific operating conditions is of extreme importance to maximize the task performance. Considering the robot in interaction with its environment, two main task phases can be identified: 1) free-space approaching motion, and 2) contact. Optimizing the controllers to deal with such task phases and (continuously) switching among them when appropriated is the main focus of this paper. Such goals become even more ambitious considering a sensorless (*i.e.*, without any force/torque sensor) position-controlled manipulator (a common situation for the most of the robots on the market). To deal with the proposed context, a sensorless optimal switching impact/force (OSIF) controller is proposed, in which the high-level controller (composed of an optimized impact controller, an optimized force controller, and a continuous switching mechanism to select the proper controller to be activated) is implemented together with the low-level controller (composed by a position control fed by an impedance control-based reference signal). In addition, the output of the switching mechanism is used to adapt the Cartesian impedance control parameters (*i.e.*, stiffness and damping parameters) to ensure a continuous and smooth transition between the two high-level controllers. Experimental tests have been performed on a Franka EMIKA panda robot to validate the proposed controller, showing impact control and force-tracking (with zero/limited force overshoots) capabilities.

Index Terms—Optimal control, impact control, interaction control, switching control, variable impedance control, industrial robots.

I. PAPER CONTRIBUTION

The here presented paper aims to propose a sensorless optimal switching impact/force (OSIF) controller, properly switching from impact control to force control (and vice versa) on the basis of the current task phase (*i.e.*, free-space approaching motion or contact). The proposed control framework is designed to be implemented on sensorless position-controlled robots. The low-level control is composed of an inner joint position controller, fed by an outer Cartesian impedance controller with the reference signals. The outer Cartesian impedance control exploits the estimation of the external wrench, obtained from the estimation of the external

joint torques provided by an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). Such an EKF is designed exploiting the position-controlled robot dynamics. The high-level controller is composed of an optimized impact controller, an optimized force controller, and a continuous switching mechanism. The optimized impact controller aims to limit the impact force during the free-space approaching motion phase. The impact modeling is employed by an LQR controller to track a reference impact velocity satisfying the specified maximum impact force. The optimized force controller aims to track a reference force during the contact phase. The coupled robot-environment modeling is employed by a State Dependent Riccati Equation (SDRE) controller. The switching mechanism aims to (continuously) select the proper controller to be employed in the current task phase (*i.e.*, determining which task phase is currently faced). A Fuzzy Logic approach is used in order to classify the current task phase (and, therefore, the controller to be selected). In addition, the output of the switching mechanism is used to adapt the Cartesian impedance control parameter (*i.e.*, stiffness and damping parameters) to ensure a continuous and smooth transitions between the two high-level controllers.

W.r.t. the algorithm earlier developed in [1] by some of the authors, the here presented approach advances the state of the art in the field. In fact, in the previous approach, the impact controller was optimized offline in a simulation environment. In addition, the simple switching mechanism doesn't allow continuous switching between the two high-level controllers.

Experimental tests have been performed to validate the proposed controller. A Franka EMIKA panda robot has been employed as a test platform. Its internal joint torque sensors have been exploited to validate the estimation of the external joint torques provided by the proposed EKF, together with the force impact and force tracking performance. An ablation study (*i.e.*, a systematic incremental validation) has been pursued to validate the capabilities of each component of the proposed control framework (*i.e.*, EKF, optimal impact control, OSIF control). Achieved results show the capabilities of the OSIF control to properly switch (*i.e.*, correctly identifying the

Fig. 1: Proposed control schema. The OSIF controller (composed by the Fuzzy Logic switching mechanism, the optimal impact controller, and the optimal force controller, the outer impedance controller, the control block for the adaptation of the stiffness and damping parameters, and the inner position controller with robot dynamics compensation) are highlighted. The proposed EKF providing the estimate of the external joint torques $\hat{\tau}_{ext}$ is also shown in the control schema.

current task phase) from impact control to force control (and vice versa), guaranteeing to satisfy the target performance (*i.e.*, limiting the impact force during the free-space approaching motion phase, and tracking the reference force avoiding force overshoots during the contact phase).

II. METHODOLOGY

The main aim of the proposed paper is the definition of the OSIF controller, capable to switch from optimal impact control to optimal force control (and vice versa) on the basis of the current task phase. To this aim, the control framework shown in Figure 1 has been implemented. The Figure highlights all the developed components defining the OSIF controller. The low-level control (composed of the inner joint position control and the outer Cartesian impedance control) is highlighted. The EKF for the estimation of the external joint torques is highlighted, showing the computation of the external interaction wrench used by the Cartesian impedance control. The high-level controller (composed of the optimal impact control, the optimal force control, the switching mechanism, and the stiffness and damping regulation block) is highlighted. In the next Sections, each main component defining the OSIF controller is analyzed.

III. RESULTS

A video showing the experimental results achieved by the OSIF controller is available at the link <https://youtu.be/64oWtLloTSY>.

An assembly task (of a gear into its shaft) has been also considered to verify the applicability of the proposed approach in a real application. Figure 2 shows the measured interaction force $f_{t,z}$ vs. the estimated interaction force $\hat{f}_{t,z}$ during the assembly task execution. Trial 1 shows a smooth insertion of the gear without pre-collisions. Trial 2, instead, shows a pre-collision between the shaft and the gear. In such a situation, the optimal force controller is switched on. After the collision, the gear slides engaging the shaft. The optimal impact control is switched on again, until the gear is fully assembled and the

Fig. 2: Estimated force (continuous line) vs. measured force (dot-dashed line) achieved by the sensorless OSIF controller during the assembly task execution. The maximum impact force $f_{t,i}^{ref,imp}$ (dashed line) is highlighted, together with the reference contact force $f_{t,i}^{ref,f}$ (dotted line).

optimal force control is again switched on. The proposed OSIF control is, therefore, able to manage the switching between controllers during the different task phases. For additional tests and analysis of the achieved results, please refer to the available video at <https://youtu.be/64oWtLloTSY>.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The presented paper proposes a sensorless optimal switching impact/force controller to deal with interaction tasks. Experimental results (involving a Franka EMIKA panda robot) validated the proposed approach, highlighting the achieved performance: high performance in the estimation of the external joint torques (and interaction wrench), satisfying the limit on the maximum impact force, high-accuracy force-tracking capabilities, and stable switching mechanism managing the transitions of the high-level controllers.

Future work is devoted to employ AI for the tuning of the control parameters, adapting them to the specific operating situation (*e.g.*, target environment stiffness, target mounted robot tool, etc.). In addition, an AI-based switching mechanism is under development.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Roveda, N. Iannacci, F. Vicentini, N. Pedrocchi, F. Braghin, and L. M. Tosatti, "Optimal impedance force-tracking control design with impact formulation for interaction tasks," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 130–136, 2015.